

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TELEVISION BROADCASTING NETWORKS OF THE DVB-T2 STANDARD

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Abstract

Integration of digital television broadcasting networks and networks of mobile operators allows to improve the work single-frequency networks of both operators, to provide more service functions for the end consumer in the context of the introduction of 5G systems, as well as to avoid overloading the used network. Tests conducted in 5G experimental areas have shown positive results with this approach.

Key words: digital broadcasting networks, network, communication systems, mobile communication, information transmission.

Relatively recently, there has been a transition from analog television broadcasting to a digital form of information transmission. First it was the DVB-T standard, and then its improved version - DVB-T2. Such a transition helped to significantly improve the quality of received programs, energy consumption, and introduce additional service functions for the consumer. Within a short time, it was possible to create an infrastructure that supports the entire existing digital broadcasting system at a qualitative level.

Simultaneously with digital broadcasting networks DVB-T and DVB-T2, standards are developing and networks mobile communication systems. With the advent of systems 4G mobile communication, which uses LTE technology, has become in high demand transmission of video content to the end user. This interest was caused by the increase in the bandwidth of the networks themselves, the appearance on the market of smartphones with a large screen, which did not justify the hopes of DVB-H mobile broadcasting technology.

Mobile transmission format video materials and television broadcasting was developed for 3G networks. Widespread he did not receive his practical implementation he was able to get only with the advent of 4G networks, using LTE technology. This version standard is called eMBMS (Evolved Multicast / Broadcast Multimedia Services). The standard defines the stacks of protocols and interfaces used and involves the creation of a new backbone network, which makes it possible to implement the transfer of media content in the mobile networks of cellular operators. Practical implementation of eMBMS technology

also revealed its shortcomings, one of which is a short cyclic prefix that acts as a guard interval. Such a short prefix, given the current density of used towers, does not 55 Vesnik svyazi 2/2021 will achieve high coverage of the area with eMBMS technology services at high speeds. The ability to adapt the transmission mode for stable reception inherent in LTE technology also creates problems. Under the condition of unstable reception, the transmitting side - a cell of the mobile communication system - goes into a mode with greater transmission noise immunity, but such a transition significantly reduces the efficiency of using the frequency spectrum.

Considering these shortcomings, for some time, an improved MBMS, the FeMBMS technology, has been proposed. It took into account the shortcomings identified during eMBMS testing. FeMBMS uses a higher density of OFDM subcarriers. This implementation made it possible to increase the guard interval, which made it possible to spread the transmitting towers of the mobile operator of the single frequency network (SFN) over long distances from each other, increasing the coverage area.

One of the features of the eMBMS technology was the conflict for the network transport resource between unicast/broadcast. The problem was solved by introducing a separate broadcast mode into FeMBMS

The use of LTE networks for broadcasting has become possible thanks to the Transport only mode, which allows you to transmit media streams of any format. For example, you can place MPEG-2 TS packets used in digital broadcasting there, as well as apply this mode to transfer any other data.

FeMBMS technology makes it possible to provide services on demand Mood (operationon-demand). This mechanism allows you to dynamically switch between unicast deliveries of media content to multicast, which significantly saves network resources. Getting access to the services implemented in the FeMBMS technology is carried out without SIM cards. Thus, the reception of services can be implemented using not only mobile cellular devices, but also fixed TVs.

Today, the transition from 4G mobile communication systems to next-generation 5G systems is underway. Against this background, the question of the further existence and development of digital TV broadcasting networks already deployed and in operation becomes relevant. One of the promising directions in this matter is the integration of the existing TV broadcasting network with the cellular operator's network.

Initially, broadcast networks are more efficient in delivering TV content to more subscribers. For TV broadcasting, the network structure of a cellular mobile operator is not optimal. This is due to the fact that the networks of TV broadcasting and mobile operators belong to different categories - HTHP (High Tower, High Power) and LTLP (Low Tower, Low Power), respectively. In this position, TV broadcasters can cover a large area with lower costs.

The essence of the proposed further development of TV broadcasting is the joint use of cellular and broadcast networks. With this approach, broadcasters' TV media streams will be transmitted not in standard frames used in DVB-T2, but in FEF (Future Extinction Frame) frames. The structure of the FEF frame format is similar to the Transport Only mode, which is already included in the FeMBMS. A distinctive feature is that, using FEF, it is possible to save a part of the transport stream for classic TV broadcasting, multiplexing it in time with the mobile operator's signal.

Conclusion.

Thus, the introduction of FeMBMS technology into the fifth generation system is beneficial for not only mobile network operators and TV broadcasters, but for media content producers. For the latter, it is an opportunity to create regional content in which the end users of a certain region are interested, as well as take into account the needs and rapidly changing interest of the target audience. Multicasting allows you to cover not only individual groups of consumers, but also take into account the interest of each of them. All this can be achieved by providing high quality at low financial costs.

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